

Against Types

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Abstract

We argue that types will become obsolete through the combined impact of strong AI and abstraction logic.

1 Why Types?

Types are everywhere, and there are good reasons for this. Here are the most important ones:

1. Types turn Church’s lambda calculus [1] into a consistent logic [2], emphasising computation and algorithms. Without types, untyped lambda calculus is inconsistent [3].
2. Types are used as lightweight formal methods, based on Milner’s adage that ‘well-typed programs cannot go wrong’ [4].
3. Types facilitate abstraction and modularity [5]. We don’t need to know what the values of a certain type are; we just need to know how operations on values of the type are supposed to behave.

2 Abstraction Logic

This section gives a short overview of abstraction logic (AL), see [6] for a comprehensive account of AL. In the third and last section we argue that AL together with the emergence of strong AI will make types—as we know them—obsolete.

AL uniquely combines two features: *general binders*, and a *single mathematical universe*. By general binders we mean a mechanism for introducing and working with general variable binding constructs. Type theory has general binders, but first-order logic and even second-order logic do not (they only have two fixed variable binding constructs: universal quantification and existential quantification). A single mathematical universe means a single realm in which all mathematical objects live. First-order logic and second-order logic have that, but type theory does not. Instead, type theory has to rely on an infinite hierarchy of universes instead of a single unified universe. This is due to Cantor’s theorem, which states that there are always more operations on mathematical objects than mathematical objects themselves. In AL, we avoid such a hierarchy by not trying to turn operations into mathematical objects; instead we admit that, in general, operations are not mathematical objects. We furthermore introduce *operators*, which are functions on operations, returning mathematical objects. *Truth values* are simply a partially ordered subset of the mathematical universe, which leads to any term also being a formula. Abstraction logic has two sound proof systems, which we call natural deduction (ND) and sequent calculus (SC), as theorems in SC are sequents, while theorems in ND are rules. SC is more general than ND because every rule is also a sequent, and every

ND proof is also an SC proof, but on the other hand ND is sound for a larger class of models. Furthermore, we know that ND is complete for any collection of abstractions—which are names for operators, operations and mathematical objects—and axioms—which are rules.

3 Why Types Will Become Obsolete

It is important to note that types remain vital today. I much prefer TypeScript to JavaScript, for example. However, looking into the future, I predict that the reasons for employing types will become obsolete. This prediction rests on two developments: the emergence of strong AI and the discovery of AL. In what follows, we counter each previously stated reason for employing types, considering the presence of strong AI and AL.

Types turn Church’s lambda calculus into a consistent logic, emphasising computation and algorithms. While type theory is based on some form of typed lambda calculus, AL is based on abstraction algebra, which is a generalisation of abstract algebra, generalising from operations to operators. Abstraction algebra is at least as capable as lambda calculus; it is straightforward to represent Peano arithmetic with primitive and general recursion [7], or the untyped lambda calculus [8]. Therefore, computations and algorithms can be directly represented in abstraction algebra and AL. But unlike type theory, AL supports *both* general binders and a single mathematical universe. This is a typical feature of informal mathematics, and by supporting it, AL forms a natural bridge between informal and formal reasoning that type theory is incapable of, by design.

Types are used as lightweight formal methods. Types have proven themselves to be uniquely effective at introducing lightweight formal methods into software engineering processes, establishing invariants that can be used for many purposes: error detection at compile time; documentation and code clarity; safety and security, such as managing concurrent operations safely; and optimisation, which exploits these invariants to generate more efficient code. With the emergence of strong AI, we will see that using AL for the purpose of formulating and establishing invariants will become lightweight enough for industrial use. Static type systems represent a form of premature optimisation of the language that invariants are expressed in; AL, on the other hand, is fully flexible and complete for any choice of abstractions and axioms (at least for natural deduction). There will be no need to press a design into the rigid constraints of an a priori and ultimately arbitrary type system; instead, the design is established and constrained by the rules of logic only. Of course, this does not apply only to AL but also to other general logics, including general type theories. But we believe that AL is especially well suited as a unified foundation for formal methods because of its general binders, single mathematical universe and algebraic roots, also making it particularly suited for AI [9].

Types facilitate abstraction and modularity. Types allow us to reason about values without having to know exactly what those values look like. This contrasts with formalisms such as set theory, where $x \in 3$ is a meaningful statement, although the way we perceive 3 as a natural number should be irrelevant. Abstraction logic, like type theory, also permits abstraction (as its name suggests). Moreover, because everything exists in a single mathematical universe, there is no need for parametric polymorphism or other type system complications: logic alone can express the invariants under which abstractions are well-behaved. This is particularly useful for building large and interconnected, yet modular, libraries. These libraries may include those that implement specific type systems, realising ‘user space type systems’¹.

¹I believe this expression is due to Makarius Wenzel.

References

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